

Data pipelines in radiation oncology: lessons from software engineering

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Introduction

Processes automation in a clinical environments is highly desirable as it reduces the workload and eliminates error-prone tasks. At our institution, the collection of patient data for research purposes historically relied on manual entries. This was the case for instance for dosimetric indices, which were not generated in structured form from the treatment planning systems used. Nowadays, the information is more structured but adequate data pipelines must be used to extract it through extract/transform/load (ETL) operations. We have developed a dosimetric index extraction pipeline that retrieves files from a PACS server and stores the results in a standard fashion. This pipeline retrieves files from an Orthanc [1] PACS server, performs calculations, categorizes patients and saves the results in a local database. The implementation of the pipeline led us to software engineering notions due to the heterogeneity of patients metadata and the ever changing nature of the hospital IT systems (e.g. software version upgrades, vocabulary used, networking rules).

Materials & Methods

A dosimetric index extraction pipeline was developed with the Python programming language and an object-oriented programming paradigm. It has four main steps: 1) query patients in a Orthanc PACS server [1], optionally from a list of patients, 2) retrieve files required for the calculations (RTDOSE, RTPLAN, RTSTRUCT) via Orthanc's REST API, 3) calculate DVHs and dosimetric indices of each structure from DICOM files using `dicompyler-core` functions [2], 4) store the results in a research database as well as in DICOM format using appropriate tags.

The first step consists in identifying targeted patients and required DICOM instances. A tree data structure representing patient's studies, series and instances in the Orthanc PACS server (figure 1, left) is built for each patient by sending GET HTTP requests to Orthanc's API. Tree objects are implemented to be lightweight to ensure that every patients in the DICOM repository can be represented in the available computer memory, so that list comparisons can be performed (e.g. to identify new patients in the PACS). Trees are subsequently filtered to dismiss unnecessary nodes. Several treatment plans for instance might be found in DICOM files, and the last chronological one is used. In step 2, the remaining nodes are used to retrieve their corresponding DICOM file.

The third step computes DVH and dosimetric indices for each anatomical structure found in the the DICOM RT files. Some structure names are mapped to others through a synonym table, to account for protocols prescribing the use of specific terms for concepts that are otherwise existing in our database

(e.g. target and prostate refer to the same anatomical structure). The computation tasks involve the virtual proxy design pattern, which controls the memory used by postponing the DVHs creation until there are needed. The handling of metadata (mainly relevant DICOM tags) is delegated to a custom *Metadata* object for each version of a treatment planning software in use, which implements the same *Metadata interface* from a *Metadata Factory* (see figure 1, b)). At our institution, two clinical software are used, which might require a version-specific interface: Oncentra Prostate (OCP) and Oncentra Brachy (OTP).

Figure 1: a), *Patient* data structure tree. b), *Metadata Factory* UML diagram.

The fourth step stores the results in a SQLite database, along with relevant metadata to categorize patients and for future analyses. The results are also written back to the DICOM files using `pydicom` [3] and moved back to the PACS server.

Results

Three concepts in software engineering were successfully implemented in our ETL pipelines. First, patient tree data structures facilitated filtering operations and allowed us to scale up efficiently with the number of patients. Second, the use of the virtual proxy design pattern allowed us to have control over the memory used. This is crucial to scale up to Big Data magnitude. Finally, having a factory method and a *Metadata* object per clinical software version was an elegant way to handle the heterogeneity of metadata.

Discussion & Conclusions

Building data pipelines in clinical environments can quickly lead to significant implementation complexity. The pipelines must be easily adaptable to an ecosystem that is constantly evolving. The use of software engineering concepts has allowed us to adequately handle each step of the pipeline, both in terms of complexity and variety of data, and to keep tab on computational resources. These concepts have shown their relevance for ETL operations, and will become crucial for Big Data endeavours in radiation oncology.

References

- [1] Jodogne S. The Orthanc Ecosystem for Medical Imaging. *J Digit Imaging*. 2018;31: 341–352.
doi:10.1007/s10278-018-0082-y
- [2] Aditya Panchal. (2018, April 4). dicompyler/dicompyler-core: DVH Interpolation (Version v0.5.4). Zenodo. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1212458>
- [3] Darcy Mason, scaramallion, rhaxton, mrbean-bremen, Jonathan Suever, Vanessa Sochat, ... Adam Klimont. (2019, January 16). pydicom/pydicom: 1.2.2 (Version v1.2.2). Zenodo.
<http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2541240>

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